

HISTORICAL FOUNDATION AND MODERN VIEW OF NEUROSURGERY

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Annotation: This article discusses ,the fundamental point of modern medicine, neurosurgery, its background and role in today. Moreover, special features and significant branches of neurosurgery were noted.

Key words: *transmits, chronic back pain, medical specialty, non-surgical care, pituitary tumor, impairments, chisels, currettes, computer-aided design.*

INTRODUSTION

All types of doctors help with our health, but some are more important than others. Neurological surgeons fix brain and nervous system problems that might have a lot of effects. Some patients may have trouble behaving or perceiving things correctly while others may have difficulty moving or suffer from severe pain. If we fix these problems by doing a surgery, the patient's life can get better right away and in a big way. A neurosurgeon is a doctor who helps people with problems in their brain, spine, and nerves. They take care of the blood vessels in the brain, the nervous system that controls our movements and feelings, and the nerves that send messages from our body to our brain. The treatment can help with different health problems like brain issues (strokes, tumors, epilepsy, and Parkinson's disease), pain in the back that lasts a long time, and even wrist pain

from using the computer too much (carpal tunnel syndrome).

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

Neurosurgery mean surgery on the nervous system. Brain surgery is a type of medical treatment for problems with the nervous system like the brain, spinal cord, and other nerves in the body. Neurosurgery covers all parts of the nervous system, not just the brain. Doctors in this field diagnose and treat patients with injuries or diseases that affect the nerves in different parts of the body. Neurosurgery is a type of medical care for adults and kids. A doctor who specializes in the brain and nervous system might use surgery or non-surgery to treat a patient with an injury or illness. In some places, you need to meet certain rules to be a legal neurosurgeon, and you have to learn in different ways too. To become a neurosurgeon in many places, you must study for at least seven years after finishing medical school.

The Incas did something called trepanation a long time ago, even before Europeans came to their land. A long time ago in a place called Al-Andalus, a man named Al-Zahrawi helped people with head and spine injuries, swelling in the brain, and bad headaches by doing surgery on them. This happened around the years 936 to 1013 AD. In ancient Rome, doctors fixed broken skulls by doing an operation on the brain. The King Henri II got hurt during jousting and Gabriel Montgomery's caused a wound that led to his death. Doctors did a simple surgery on him to try and help. Two skilled doctors named Ambroise Paré and Andreas Vesalius tried unsuccessfully to cure Henri using their own techniques. A long time ago in China, a man named Hua Tuo made something called mafeisan that puts people to sleep so doctors can do surgeries on their brain. In 1879, William Macewen was the first surgeon to remove a brain tumor successfully without using any equipment, only by observing the patient's symptoms. A long time ago, two doctors in England did an important operation to remove a tumor from someone's brain. The first doctor found the tumor using a technique developed by

someone else, while the second doctor actually removed the tumor by operating on the exposed brain. They did it differently than how people did it before. On March 16, 1907, a doctor named Hermann Schloffer was able to take out a tumor from the pituitary gland inside a person's head. He was the first person to do this successfully.

Lobotomy was a medical treatment where doctors cut connections in the front part of the brain to try and help people with mental illnesses. Another name for it is leucotomy. A doctor from Portugal named António Egas Moniz created a medical process and won the Nobel Prize in 1949. After the surgery, some patients got better in some ways, but many had problems and sometimes they were serious. People disagreed about the procedure when it was first used because they were worried about whether it would do more good than harm. It is not often used for treatment anymore because it does not respect patients' rights. Neurosurgery got better because of really good tools. Modern tools used in brain surgery are chisels, suction tubes, robots, and other instruments that help doctors cut, remove, and manipulate the brain. Most of these new tools have been used in medicine for quite a while. The main thing that sets apart these tools used in brain surgery is how accurate they were made. These tools are made very precisely with edges that are only a tiny amount off from what is planned. New tools like power saws and robots are now being used more often in brain surgery. The University of Utah made a tool that helps computers design and make things. It uses pictures to show a robot where to drill holes in someone's head. Brain surgery covers a lot of different problems such as head injuries and bleeding in the brain. Most basic hospitals follow this procedure

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Specialized areas have been created for taking care of unique and challenging situations. There are some hospitals that have special doctors who only work on certain parts of the brain, and they work together with other doctors

who do all kinds of brain surgeries. Advanced techniques that use pictures of the brain are used to help diagnose and treat problems in the brain. Some brain surgeries use special types of MRI scanning called intra-operative MRI and functional MRI. In regular surgery, the doctor cuts open the skull to reach the brain. Doctors now use microscopes and endoscopes to perform surgeries through smaller openings. Using small openings in the skull along with powerful microscopes to see the brain can give really good outcomes. The old techniques are still used in accidents or urgent circumstances. Microsurgery is a type of surgery that is used for many parts of the brain and nervous system. Doctors use small blood vessel techniques in surgery to bypass blocked arteries in the brain and neck. Doctors use powerful microscopes to see and carefully operate on an aneurysm. Minimal-invasive spine surgery is when doctors use tiny tools like microscopes or endoscopes to operate on your spine. Small surgeries like microdiscectomy, laminectomy, and artificial disc replacement use microsurgery.

Doctors can use a special technique called stereotaxy to reach a small area in the brain by making a tiny hole. This is a medical procedure that is used to treat Parkinson's disease or Alzheimer's disease. It involves putting small wires or special medicine into the brain with high precision. A way of doing surgery that combines two methods can maybe help remove bleeding inside the brain's ventricles. Surgery that uses technology to help guide it is becoming more common. It is called surgical navigation, computer-assisted surgery, navigated surgery, or stereotactic navigation. Just like how a car or phone GPS works, image-guided surgery systems use cameras or electromagnetic fields to show the surgeon's movements and the patient's body on computer screens in the operating room. It helps the surgeon operate more accurately. Researchers use real-time brain mapping to find specific parts of the brain that do different things. They do this by using a method called electrocorticography (ECoG).

Neurosurgeons often use a special type of surgery called minimally

invasive endoscopic surgery when it is suitable. Doctors use a method called endoscopic endonasal surgery to treat certain kinds of brain tumors and repair leaks in the fluid that surrounds the brain and spinal cord. Doctors use ventricular endoscopy to treat problems like bleeding inside the brain, too much fluid in the brain, a type of cyst called a colloid cyst, and a parasitic infection in the brain. At times, neurosurgeons and ear, nose and throat surgeons work together to do endonasal endoscopy. Neurosurgeons fix problems with the face and skull, and with the fluid in the brain and spine. They sometimes work with other doctors who specialize in the face and plastic surgery. Cranioplasty is a surgery for skull bones that didn't grow properly. Doctors who work with children's brains do this surgery, sometimes with doctors who work with skin and muscles. These same brain doctors also use a special kind of radiation therapy to treat tumors and abnormal blood vessels in the brain with help from radiation specialists. Surgical methods called Gamma knife, Cyberknife, and Novalis Radiosurgery are also used.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, it should be noted that, illnesses affecting the brain and nervous system are the main reason why people become disabled or die. This happens a lot all over the world. Every year, many people around the world need to be treated by a type of doctor called a neurosurgeon because they have conditions like brain injuries or too much fluid in their brains. In total, about 22.6 million people need this kind of care, and around 13.8 million of them need to have surgery. Despite efforts to make healthcare better around the world, this still happens. Neurosurgical care is very important in both local and global health talks.

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